

РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ ПРАКТИЧЕСКОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ВИКИ-ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ УЧЕБНОЙ ДИСЦИПЛИНЫ «АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК ДЛЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕЛЕЙ» СТУДЕНТОВ НЕЯЗЫКОВЫХ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТЕЙ

WIKI TECHNOLOGIES PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION WITHIN “ENGLISH FOR SPECIAL PURPOSES” AS NON-LINGUISTIC STUDENTS ACADEMIC SUBJECT

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В статье рассматривается методический потенциал вики-технологий, актуальность применения которых объясняется внедрением в образовательный процесс комплекса вспомогательных инновационно-дидактических средств. В работе сформулировано определение термина «вики-технология». Выделены и охарактеризованы дидактические свойства и методические функции вики-технологии. Предложен алгоритм развития языковых умений и навыков на основе вики-технологии студентов, обучающихся по направлению подготовки 45.03.02 «Лингвистика». В результате определены основные принципы реализации практического применения вики-технологий на занятиях по иностранному языку.

The article examines the methodological potential of wiki technologies, the relevance of which is explained by the introduction of a complex of auxiliary innovative and didactic tools into the educational process. The paper defines the term "wiki technology". The didactic properties and methodological functions of wiki technology are highlighted and characterized. An algorithm for the development of language skills based on wiki technology of students studying in the field of training 45.03.02 "Linguistics" is proposed. As a result, the basic principles of implementing the practical application of wiki technologies in foreign language classes are determined.

Ключевые слова: вики-технологии, языковой образование, инновационные методы, информационные технологии, дидактические принципы.

Key words: wiki technologies, language education, innovative methods, information technologies, didactic principles.

R **elevance.**
The modern education system is characterized by a constant dynamic search for ways to improve the effectiveness of the educational process, in which special attention is paid to the issues of individualisation of learning, development of the creative potential of students, extra curriculum work active forms organisation, which are aimed at developing self-education and independent thinking skills, as well as communication skills.

The beginning of the 21st century is characterized by the informatisation of language teaching, which is based on the use of information and communication technologies, the main criteria of which are rationalisation, objectification, formalisation and planning, as well as a change in the role of the lecturer and reaching a wider audience.

Problem possessing.

The level of mastering the foreign language at various levels of linguistic education is strictly governed by the main document regulating the academic process in general – the Higher Education Federal State Academic Standards. Thus modern scientific doctrine includes many works in which scientists substantiate and develop various methods of teaching a foreign language using modern information and communication technologies among which the wiki-technologies are that is directly targeted at on the one hand increasing the students motivation to extra curriculum activities, and on the other hand expands the opportunities to improve language skills with the help of contemporary digital technologies.

Materials and methods.

A mixed-method research design (qualitative and quantitative research design) was used to find the effectiveness of developing grammar skills in teaching writing, as well as to collect data for the current study as it was used to describe attitudes, beliefs, opinions and other types of information.

Research results.

The wiki was first created by programmer Ward Cunningham in 1995. Its main purpose was to use the wiki service as an internal database. At the same time, the name of the service “wiki” was borrowed from the Hawaiian language (trans. wiki-wiki – “quick”) and means quick access to information. In 2000, with the appearance of the first online encyclopedia “Wikipedia”, where anyone can become the author of an article, the social wiki service became world famous.

Wiki technology should be understood as a technology for constructing web systems that are designed for collective development, storage, and structuring of text, hypertext, various files, and multimedia. From the point of view of P.V. Sysoev, who specializes in information and communication technologies in foreign language teaching, the concept of “wiki technology” provides for one of the types of Web 2.0 services, which allows one person or a group of people who are remote from each other to work on creating a single document, and also make various changes and additions to it.

It is noted that wiki technology is one of the Internet resources that allows an individual or a group of individuals to view the pages of websites, as well as edit them, create new websites, publish their documents, take part in the discussion of published information, view the history of changes made and so on [4, p. 7].

The practical application of wiki technologies in foreign language classes led to the formation of a set of basic didactic principles for the implementation of such technologies, which make it possible to significantly intensify the learning process. So, according to P.V. Sysoev, these include:

- Firstly, building an individual educational trajectory by students and lecturers;
- Secondly, the implementation of pedagogical learning technology in cooperation (i.e. student-lecturer interaction);
- Thirdly, the development of independent learning activities.

Let’s take a closer look at each of them.

The first basic didactic principle is building an individual educational trajectory for students and lecturers. From the point of view of P.V. Sysoev, an individual educational trajectory is a personal way of achieving a set educational goal and/or educational task by a specific student. It corresponds to his abilities, motives, interests and needs. It should be noted that building an individual trajectory for achieving a set goal is carried out by the student together with the lecturer, both with

the help of existing and proposed elements for general training, and with the help of a number of additional methodological elements, which include [2, p. 32]:

- Alternative forms and methods of teaching (case method, project method, educational discussions, etc.);
- Alternative forms and methods of mastering educational material: (Arkady Zilberman method, programmed training);
- Alternative control methods (tasks that involve a creative approach on the part of the student);
- Alternative training content;
- Alternative time and speed of mastering educational material and the formation of the necessary competencies of the student to the required level.

According to P.V. Sysoev, the main function of a teacher in the process of a student choosing an individual educational path is approving such a choice and teaching the student the ability to realistically assess their strengths, knowledge, abilities, educational needs and interests in order for the student to choose the right individual path of education [1, p. 7]. A.V. Filatova notes that the lecturer's implementation of educational and methodological support of the educational process should be built on the principle of redundancy and alternativeness, and it should provide for both the presence of multi-level tasks and alternative creative works on the problem being studied. Thus, the lecturer helps the student see different ways to achieve a specific goal and choose the most suitable one from this set.

In the process of building an individual educational trajectory of learning a foreign language through wiki technology, students have the following choice:

- Firstly, work in pairs or in a group. For example, developing oral communication skills through wiki technology, when several students work on the content of one document;
- Secondly, create a “product” (for example, a text) in written form on a wiki server or post a video file with an oral monologue or dialogue;
- Thirdly, control over the development of existing teachings only by the lecturer or the lecturer and groupmates (with the help of a microblog, where the process of implementing the project is discussed, and so on);
- Fourthly, the timing of conducting and presenting the results of the wiki project (from two weeks to a quarter) and so on.

However, it is important to emphasize that the implementation of this principle of wiki technologies practical application in foreign language classes is possible under the following conditions:

- A desire to learn something and the lecturer's ability to build the educational process of a particular student along an individual trajectory;
- Providing the student with the opportunity to make a choice in building an individual educational trajectory;
- Development by the lecturer of educational alternative material on the specific topic being studied, based on the principle of redundancy;
- The lecturer's ability to conduct pedagogical observations of the student and monitor the student's independent learning activities in order to make the necessary adjustments to his learning process.

The second basic didactic principle, the principle of implementing the pedagogical technology of learning in cooperation, provides for the creation of conditions for the implementation of active joint educational and cognitive activities of students in different educational situations in which students and the lecturer take part [1, p. 9].

It should be noted that the implementation of the practical application of wiki technology based on this principle is characterized by the following specific features:

- The relationship of all participants in the wiki project;
- Personal responsibility of each participant for their own successes and the successes of their groupmates;
- Joint educational, cognitive, creative and other activities of students in a group;
- Socialization of students' activities in a group;
- A general assessment of the group's work, the formation of which is based on an assessment of the form of students communication in the group along with the academic results of the work.

The interdependence of participants in joint learning activities is one of the key conditions for the implementation of the practical application of wiki technologies in foreign language classes. It consists of the following:

- Firstly, a single goal of the project, the achievement of which is possible only by dividing it into a set of component tasks and solving them in the process of joint activity of the entire group of project participants;
- Secondly, the distribution of educational material in such a way that each project participant possesses only the amount of information or material that is necessary to solve the general task;
- Thirdly, the use of a single set of equipment for all participants (Internet pages);
- Fourthly, encouragement and evaluation are the same for all group members.

Each group receives one specific task, which requires the participation of each group member in its implementation, and therefore roles are distributed among them and a separate segment of work is designated. Each group is given one set of necessary materials (one text, one Internet page on which the wiki project will be carried out, etc.). It should also be noted that the mark for completing the entire wiki project is also given to the entire group.

The third principle, the principle of developing independent learning activities among students in the process of practical application of wiki technologies in foreign language classes, provides for the ability of students to independently extract information, receive it, synthesize it, produce new information and distribute the received information.

It is also emphasized that the extent to which students will be capable of self-education throughout their lives by the time they graduate from the university depends on the development of such students' skills in independent learning activities during the process of studying at the university [3, p. 34]. According to contemporary researchers position the concept of "independent educational activity" should be understood as one of the types of cognitive activity that is regulated and controlled by the student as a subject of this activity and which is aimed at mastering subject knowledge and skills and cultural and historical experience [2, p. 43].

Thus, the researcher believes that the student's participation in independent productive learning activities means that he:

- Is included in determining the goals of mastering a foreign language and correlates them with their real interests and needs;
- Actively takes part in designing the final result of the foreign language acquisition product and determining the criteria for its evaluation;
- Together with the lecturer and his groupmates, selects the most appropriate and effective forms and methods of teaching;
- Monitors the process and success of one's progress in language acquisition;
- Evaluates real achievements and possibilities of using a foreign language in real activities;
- Evaluates the productivity and experience of his educational activities;

– Evaluates himself, determines the “I-position”, i.e. he does not take into account the opinions of others.

The practical use of wiki technologies in foreign language classes significantly increases the volume of independent learning activities of students, which, together with building an individual educational trajectory, actually determines their preparation for active independent activity in the modern rapidly changing world.

The above-mentioned principles for implementing the practical application of wiki technologies in foreign language classes are specific requirements for the function of a lecturer in the educational process. Thus, the competence of a foreign language lecturer in the field of using wiki technologies requires both the knowledge and skills to organise the learning process itself and educational interaction by the student through a separate type of information and communication technologies, as well as the coordination and moderation of the educational process.

Conclusion.

Thus the main task of a lecturer when using wiki technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language is to create such pedagogical and methodological conditions within which students have the opportunity to learn independently how to:

- Receive, extract, synthesize, classify, summarise, create information;
- Formulate the problem and indicate the purpose of learning (at a specific stage or within the framework of a specific topic, educational section, etc.);
- Choose the most appropriate option for solving the problem (goal);
- Work to solve the problem individually or in groups, while distributing responsibilities and sharing responsibility for the implementation of the designated area of work;
- Develop communication and cooperation skills;
- Use a foreign language as a means of communication and wiki technology as a means to satisfy cognitive needs and interests;
- Develop the ability to analyse one’s educational activities and its results (reflection).

So, among the basic principles for implementing the practical application of wiki technologies in foreign language classes, we can highlight: building an individual educational trajectory by the student and lecturer, implementing the pedagogical technology “learning in collaboration” and developing students’ skills in independent learning activities.

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